

IMPACT OF ACCELERATED CARBONATION CURING ON THE STRENGTH AND DURABILITY CHARACTERISTICS OF GGBS CONCRETE

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Abstract: This study investigates the impact of Accelerated Carbonation Curing (ACC) on the strength and durability of concrete with Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS) as a partial cement replacement, ranging from 0% to 60%. The evaluation included compressive strength as well as durability parameters such as water absorption, chloride permeability, sorptivity, and acid resistance. Additionally, microstructural analysis was performed on concrete specimens with 0% and 40% GGBS using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and X-ray Diffraction (XRD). Two different curing regimes were applied: one set of specimens was subjected to conventional water curing, while the other underwent carbonation curing for 12 hours, followed by water curing until the age of 3 days, after which they were stored in sealed plastic bags until the testing period. Experimental results indicated that although early carbonation enhanced initial strength, the long-term strength gain was not significant. Carbonated specimens exhibited lower water absorption at 1, 3, and 28 days, along with reduced sorptivity, enhanced resistance to chloride permeability, and greater acid resistance compared to water-cured specimens. The incorporation of GGBS improved strength and reduced water absorption, with 40% replacement identified as the optimal level. GGBS concrete also demonstrated lower sorptivity and superior resistance to chloride penetration and acid exposure than the control mix. Microstructural analysis revealed that carbonation led to the conversion of calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) into calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), contributing to increased strength. Additionally, concrete containing 40% GGBS exhibited a denser microstructure compared to the control mix, further enhancing its durability.

Keywords: Accelerated carbonation curing, GGBS concrete, compressive strength, durability, microstructure analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon dioxide (CO_2) emissions from human activities are a significant contributor to global warming and climate change. The impact of global warming is already evident, with shrinking glaciers and earlier ice breakups in lakes. Over the coming century, climate change is expected to intensify, largely depending on the volume of heat-trapping gases such as CO_2 , CH_4 , and N_2O released into the atmosphere, as well as the Earth's response to these emissions. Therefore, it is crucial to explore methods for capturing and storing CO_2 to mitigate its environmental impact.

Concrete is one of the most widely used materials worldwide, but its production significantly contributes to CO_2 emissions. The cement industry alone is responsible for nearly 5% of global

CO₂ emissions (Worrell et al., 2001), primarily due to fossil fuel combustion and limestone decomposition during cement manufacturing. Capturing and utilizing CO₂ in concrete production could provide an environmentally beneficial solution.

Curing freshly cast concrete is an essential process that facilitates the hydration reaction in cement, improving both early-age strength and long-term durability. Proper curing begins immediately after placement and finishing, ensuring optimal temperature and moisture retention for an extended period. The duration and type of curing required depend on several factors, including:

- Mix proportions
- Size and shape of the concrete structure
- Required strength
- Expected environmental exposure
- Ambient weather conditions

By optimizing curing methods and exploring CO₂ sequestration in concrete, sustainable practices can be integrated into construction, reducing the industry's carbon footprint while enhancing concrete performance.

2. COMMONLY USED CURING TECHNIQUES

- **Water Curing:** This method involves keeping the concrete surface continuously moist by applying water. This can be achieved through methods such as sprinkling, ponding, or using wet burlap or mats. Water curing helps maintain the necessary moisture for the hydration process, ensuring proper strength development.
- **Wet Covering:** Wet covering involves placing materials like wet burlap, hessian cloth, or other moisture-retaining fabrics on the concrete surface. These materials are kept damp to prevent moisture loss from the concrete, which is essential for proper hydration.
- **Covering with Plastic Sheets:** Plastic sheeting or film can be used to cover the concrete surface. This technique prevents moisture evaporation by creating a barrier, which helps retain the moisture necessary for curing.
- **Chemical Curing Compounds:** Chemical curing compounds are applied as a liquid spray onto the concrete surface. These compounds form a thin, impermeable film that reduces water evaporation from the concrete surface, thereby aiding in moisture retention.
- **Steam Curing:** In steam curing, concrete is exposed to steam in an enclosed environment, typically in a curing chamber. This technique accelerates the curing process and enhances early-age strength, particularly useful in precast concrete manufacturing.
- **Curing Blankets:** Insulated curing blankets can be used to maintain the temperature and moisture levels of concrete. These blankets are especially useful in cooler weather to prevent the concrete from freezing and to ensure proper curing.
- **Hydrostatic Pressure Curing:** This technique involves immersing the concrete in a tank of water or using a controlled water system to apply hydrostatic pressure. It is used for specific applications and helps maintain consistent curing conditions.

Figure 1: **Sprinkling Water Curing** (<https://blog.yellowpages-uae.com/methods-of-curing-concrete/>)

Figure 2: **Curing by Ponding method** (<https://www.quora.com/What-is-the-meaning-of-curing-in-civil-engineering>)

Figure 3: **Membrane curing** (<https://www.tradeindia.com/fp2329434/Concrete-Curing-Membrane-For-Road-Base.html>)

Figure 4: **Steam curing** (<https://www.shutterstock.com/video/clip-4155103-stock-footage-surgut-july-washing-hot-steam-curing-of-the-plastic-barrels-for-reuse-july-in.html>)

3. ACCELERATED CARBONATION CURING

Precast concrete accounts for approximately 20-30% of the total concrete industry (Glass et al., 2001). In this sector, steam curing is commonly employed to achieve high strength in a shorter period. This method involves creating an environment with high temperature (40-70°C) and humidity (95%) to accelerate cement hydration. While steam curing enhances the rate of strength development, it can lead to potential issues at later stages and demands significant energy consumption. Consequently, carbonation curing has emerged as a promising alternative. This method not only reduces energy use but also minimizes CO₂ emissions, addressing some of the environmental concerns associated with traditional steam curing.

Figure 5: Laboratory process of carbonation curing (Zhang et al., (2017))

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE WORK

This study aims to examine the impact of carbonation curing on the properties of concrete incorporating GGBS. It focuses on utilizing industrial waste in concrete while implementing an innovative curing technique to enhance its performance. The research compares the effects of CO₂ curing and conventional water curing on various concrete properties.

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several research studies have focused on Impact of Accelerated Carbonation Curing on the Strength and Durability Characteristics of GGBS Concrete.

Lye et al. (2016): Analyzed data from 227 studies across 35 countries, finding that GGBS increases carbonation rates, especially at higher contents. The study suggested revising Eurocode 2 for GGBS concrete and noted that carbonation could exceed cover requirements before 50 years.

Ekolu et al. (2016): Reviewed curing effects on natural carbonation, finding that three days of curing stabilized long-term strength for concrete with up to 30% fly ash or 50% GGBS. Curing methods had minimal impact on natural carbonation behavior.

Li et al. (2018): Studied secondary water curing (SW) after steam-autoclave curing. SW curing improved strength and durability, reducing chloride permeability and carbonation depth by up to 80.9% at 360 days.

Zhang et al. (2020): Investigated carbonation curing effects on Portland cement concrete. Higher w/c ratio concrete showed greater carbonation depth, while lower w/c ratio concrete had better resistance to weathering carbonation.

Oliveira et al. (2019): Examined fire-damaged concrete, finding that high temperatures and rapid cooling reduced durability but did not significantly advance carbonation depth under slow cooling.

Akki et al. (2021): Evaluated carbonation effects on strength and durability using fly ash, GGBS, rice husk ash, and metakaolin. Specimens in an accelerated carbonation chamber showed varied effects based on cement replacements.

Merah et al. (2021): Studied marble powder as a partial cement replacement. Higher marble powder content increased carbonation depth and slightly reduced compressive strength, but remained within acceptable limits.

Samson et al. (2022): Investigated accelerated carbonation curing (ACC) on Guinea Corn Husk Ash (GCHA) blended concrete. Found that 10% GCHA had the highest sorptivity, with sorptivity decreasing over curing time, improving durability.

Hwalla et al. (2023): Examined ACC on alkali-activated slag concrete blocks. CO₂ uptake reached 12.8% binder mass, reducing the carbon footprint by 46% while improving compressive strength and water absorption.

Inam et al. (2023): Evaluated carbonation rates in different climates. Found that Afghanistan had the highest carbonation depth, with a prediction model accurately estimating carbonation rates across regions.

Bawab et al. (2024): Assessed ACC with calcium carbide residue (CCR) in concrete. CCR increased CO₂ uptake, with 5-10% replacement providing optimal performance. Extended curing improved sequestration and reduced the carbon footprint.

6. DISCUSSION

This study examined the impact of accelerated carbonation curing on the compressive strength, water absorption, chloride permeability, sorptivity, and acid resistance of GGBS concrete. Microstructural analysis was conducted using SEM and XRD techniques. Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

- Concrete mixes incorporating GGBS exhibited higher compressive strength than the control mix at both early and later stages, attributed to the fine particle size of GGBS. The optimal replacement level was identified as 35%, yielding the highest strength.

Additionally, increasing the GGBS content led to a reduction in water absorption, chloride permeability, and sorptivity, enhancing durability. The acid resistance of GGBS concrete was superior to that of the control mix, with the 45% replacement level providing the highest resistance to acid attack. Microstructural analysis revealed that concrete containing GGBS had a denser structure compared to the control mix, contributing to its improved performance.

- **Compressive Strength:** Carbonation curing increased compressive strength due to the formation of calcite, replacing calcium hydroxide. However, the rate of strength gain was slower due to limited water availability. At 42 days, water-cured samples exhibited higher strength than carbonation-cured samples.
- **Durability:** Water absorption and sorptivity were lower in carbonation-cured samples at all ages, as calcium carbonate formation improved durability. Chloride permeability was significantly reduced at 3 days in carbonation-cured samples, but the difference decreased as hydration progressed.
- **Acid Resistance:** Carbonation-cured samples demonstrated greater resistance to acid attack compared to water-cured specimens, with significantly lower strength loss upon acid exposure.
- **Microstructural Analysis:** SEM and XRD analyses indicated a substantial reduction in calcium hydroxide content and a notable increase in calcium carbonate in carbonation-cured samples. This transformation resulted in a denser microstructure, leading to higher strength and lower porosity in the concrete mix.

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